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THE SIGNIFICANCE OF MUTATIONS IN THE INTERLEUKIN-1B GENE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ATONIC POSTPARTUM HEMORRHAGE.....10

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MEDICAL AND PROPHYLACTIC TECHNOLOGIES OF MONITORING OF ATMOSPHERIC AIR POLLUTION BY CHEMICAL POLLUTANTS AND ISSUES OF STUDYING THE PATHOGENESIS OF DISEASES OF THE POPULATION ASSOCIATED WITH EXPOSURE TO ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS.....17
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THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF TRANSFORMATION OF TRAINING, RETRAINING AND CONTINUING PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION OF MANAGERS IN THE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....23

THERAPY

4. **Kityan A. Sergey.**
COMPREHENSIVE CHARACTERIZATION OF THE CURRENT EPIDEMIOLOGICAL SITUATION REGARDING THE INCIDENCE AND PREVALENCE OF CHRONIC HEART FAILURE(LITERARY REVIEW).....30

SURGERY

5. **Arziev A Ismoil, Mamanov Ch Muxammad., Arzieva B Gulnora.**
DIFFERENTIATED SURGICAL TACTICS FOR COMPLICATED FORMS OF LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS.....36
6. **Mamanov Ch. Muxammad., Arziev A. Ismoil, Arzieva B. Gulnora.**
POSSIBILITIES OF MODERIN RADIATION METODS IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS AND ITS COMPLICATIONS.....44
7. **Rustamov U. Sardor, Arziev A. Ismoil.**
CLINICAL RATIONALE FOR MINIMALLY INVASIVE INTERVENTIONS IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS WITH A HIGH RISK OF SURGERY AND ANESTHESIA.....52
8. **Pakirdinov S. Alisher, Nuritdinov T. Arifjon., Temirov Ch. Pulat.**
SURGICAL TREATMENT OF MEDIAGASTRIC ULCERS.....62
9. **Ikramova D. Farida, Musashaykhov T. Khusanbay.**
ANTISEPTICS IN THE TREATMENT OF PURULENT COMPLICATIONS AFTER ABDOMINAL OPERATIONS.....70
10. **Ruziboyev A. Sanjar, Sadikov A. Rustam. Allaberdiev A. Ne'mat.**
EFFICIENCY COMPARISON OF A MODIFIED METHOD FOR ALLOPLASTY OF INGUINAL HERNIA IN AN EXPERIMENTAL.....75
11. **Musashaykhov T. Khusanbay, Ikramova D. Farida, Musashaykhov Kh. Umidjon.**
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE COMPLEX TREATMENT OF PUTUROUS DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES.....83
12. **Ahmedov K. Gayrat, Tashkenbayev R. Firdavs, Gulamov M. Olimjon, Toirov S. Abduxomit.**
BARIATRIC SURGERY AND THEIR COMPLICATIONS.....91

13. **Khursanov E. Yokub, Makhmudov B. Saydinjon, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar.**
MODERN METHODS OF TREATMENT OF NON-TENSIONED HERNIOPLASTY FOR UMBILICAL HERNIA.....100
14. **ABDUVALIEVA M. Chulpanoy, KADIROV Z. Komiljon, KHALILOV K. Shukrullo**
A NUMBER OF ERRORS IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF ACUTE APPENDICITIS IN CHILDREN.....109

CHILDREN SURGERY

15. **Khalilov K. Shukrullo, Abduvalieva M. Chulpanoy, Kadirov Z. Komiljon.**
TREATMENT AND DIAGNOSIS OF DUODENAL ULCER DISEASE IN CHILDREN.115

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

16. **Eshonkulov T. Golibjon.**
FUNCTIONAL DISORDERS AND THEIR PREVENTION IN DENTAL DISEASES.....120
17. **Hojiyev H. Xurshid.**
THE ROLE OF PATHOGENETIC FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHRONIC APICAL PERIODONTITIS.....125
18. **Rizaev A. Eler, Khasanov K. Fazyl.**
THE RESULTS OF STUDIES OF THE STATE OF ANS IN PATIENTS WITH GLOSSODYNIA.....131
19. **Turaeva A. Firuza.**
IMMUNOBIOCHEMICAL MARKERS IN PATIENTS WITH GENERALIZED PARODONTITIS.....136
20. **Bekjanova E. Olga, Olimdjonov J. Kamron.**
MECHANISMS OF COMORBIDITY OF PERIODONTITIS AND INFLAMMATORY BOWEL PATHOLOGY.....144
21. **Badriddinov B. Baxrom.**
INDICATIONS FOR EARLY DIAGNOSIS AND ORTHODONTIC EXAMINATION OF HIGH JAW PROTRUSIONS IN CHILDREN.....151
22. **Eshonkulov Sh.B.**
THE EFFECT OF ANTIBACTERIAL PHOTODYNAMIC THERAPY ON THE SENSITIVITY OF MICROBES ISOLATED FROM YOUNG CHILDREN WITH PURULENT-INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF THE MAXILLOFACIAL REGION.....160
23. **Idiyev E. Gayrat, Rakhimov Sh. Shokhrukh.**
INDICATIONS FOR DETERMINING THE CONDITION OF THE ORAL ORGANS IN PATIENTS WITH RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS.....166
24. **Fattakhov A. Ravshan, Nuritdinov A. Ulugbek.**
DISC DISLOCATIONS OF THE TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINTS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....171

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

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SURGICAL TREATMENT OF CONGENITAL ATRESIA OF THE EXTERNAL AUDITORY CANAL IN CHILDREN.....177
26. **Gulyamov B. Sherzod., Karabaev E. Khurram., Khamrakulova O. Nargiza.**
DIAGNOSIS OF CONGENITAL ANOMALIES OF THE EXTERNAL AND MIDDLE EAR IN CHILDREN.....190

27. **NASRETDINOVA T. Makhzuna., OMONOVA Sh. Maftuna**
SURUNKALI POLIPOZ RINOSINUSITLARNI DAVOSINI
OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....199

PEDIATRICS

28. **Kadirov Z. Komiljon, Abduvalieva M. Chulpanoy, Khalilov K. Shukrullo.**
ACUTE PURULENT DESTRUCTIVE PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN.....205

PSYCHONEUROLOGY

29. **Khakimova Z. Sakhiba, Khamdamova K., Bektashev B. Rakhmatullo, Abdullayeva Z. Kamola.**
THE SIGNIFICANCE OF LIQUORODYNAMIC DISTURBANCES IN THE
PATHOGENESIS OF DISCIRCULATORY ENCEPHALOPATHY 380.....211
30. **Yanova U. Elvira.**
ASSESSMENT OF CIRCULATORY DISORDERS IN THE VERTEBROBASILAR ZONE
IN KIMMERLE ANOMALY.....217

ANESTEZIOLOGY

31. **Nematulloev K. Tukhtasin , G'oyibov S. Salim.**
THE INFLUENCE OF SPINAL ANESTHESIA ON THE PROLONGATION OF THE QT
INTERVAL IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS.....226
32. **Sadikova A.Minura.**
THE QUESTION OF CHOOSING THE OPTIMAL OPTION OF ANESTHESIOLOGICAL
MANAGEMENT WHEN CARRYING OUT RECONSTRUCTIVE PLASTIC SURGERY IN
PATIENTS WITH POST-CLEAR CONTRACTURES OF THE FACE, NECK AND
CHEST.....233
33. **Sadikova A.Minura.**
ALGORITHM FOR MAINTAINING AIRWAY PATESTITV FOR VARIOUS CLINICAL
SITUATIONS RELATED TO CONTRACTURES NECK DURING OPERATIVE
INTERVENTIONS IN RECONSTRUCTIVE PLASTIC SURGERY.....240

ONCOLOGY AND RADIOLOGY

34. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Ulmasov G. Firdavs, Rakhimov Kh. Zhakhongir.**
BRONCHOPULMONARY COMPLICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH LARYNGEAL
CANCER.....248
35. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Ulmasov G. Firdavs, Rakhimov Kh. Zhakhongir.**
CLINICO-MORPHOLOGICAL GROUPING OF BENIGN TUMOURS, CYSTS,
GYPERPLASTIC AND DYSTROPHIC TUMOUR-LIKE DISEASESOF THE
LARYNX.....254
36. **Ruziboyev A. Sanjar, Nosirov B. Akhtam, Amonov R. Ravshanovich.**
RESULTS OF TREATMENT WITH ACUTE GASTRIC BLEEDING DUE TO STOMACH
TUMORS.....261
37. **Zhumanov E. Ziyadulla, Khamidov A. Obid, Gaybullayev O, Sherzod.**
MORPHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF FIBROBLASTIC MENINGIOMA OF THE BRAIN
DETERMINED BY MAGNETIC RESONANCE TOMOGRAPHY EXAMINATION.....268
38. **Khamidov A. Obid, Zhumanov E. Ziyadulla, Beknazarova N, Xolniso.**
MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF XANTHOGRANULEMATOSIS CHOLECYSTITIS
DETERMINED BY ULTRASOUND EXAMINATION.....274

39. **Ametova S. Alie, Khodjibekova M. Yulduz, Ziyadullaev Kh. Shukhrat.**
ULTRASOUND PATTERNS INDICATING OSTEOCHONDRAL CHANGES IN MEDIUM AND SMALL JOINTS OF THE EXTREMITIES VARY AMONG THE PRIMARY TYPES OF ARTHROPATHY.....280

REHABILITATION AND SPORTS MEDICINE

40. **Khudoykulova V. Farida, Kalonov S. Sohibjon.**
THE ROLE OF LIFESTYLE MODIFICATION AND EATING HABITS IN NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEAS.....291

MORPHOLOGY

41. **Oripov S. Firdavs, Togayeva S. Gulnora.**
REACTIVE CHANGES IN THE MORPHOFUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE PANCREAS IN VARIOUS PATHOLOGICAL CONDITIONS OF ORGANS AND SYSTEMS OF THE BODY (REVIEW ARTICLE).....299
42. **Kuliyev A. Azad, Karabaev G. Aminjon.**
A POINT ASSESSMENT OF THE GENERAL CONDITION OF RATS THAT SUFFERED A 10-MINUTE CLINICAL DEATH.....311
43. **Kuliyev A. Azad, Karabaev G. Aminjon.**
DYNAMICS OF CHANGES IN THE RELATIONSHIP OF HORMONES OF THE REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM OF FEMALE RATS IN THE POST-INTENSIVE CARE PERIOD, AFTER MODELING A 10-MINUTE CLINICAL DEATH.....317
44. **Khamidova M. Farida, Ismailov M. Jasur, Sulaymanova J. Mariya.**
PATHOMORPHOFUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE LARRYNGE UNDER NORMAL AND PATHOLOGICAL CONDITIONS IN EXPERIMENTAL LARYNGITIS.....324
45. **Radjabov B. Akhtam.**
MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF INDICATORS OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF MALES IN POSTNATAL ONTOGENESIS AND IN CHRONIC ALCOHOLISM.....334
46. **Khamidova M. Farida, Yakubov Z. Munis.**
TRANSFORMATION OF THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE OF THE ARTIFICIAL VAGINA CREATED FROM THE LARGE INTESTINE.....339
47. **Urunova A. Mashxura, Pirmatov V. Salikh, Sadullayev E. Sadikjon.**
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN MYOCARDIAL STRUCTURE DURING DEATH OF PREMATURE DICHORIAL DIAMNIOTIC TWINS.....349
48. **Toshmamatov N. Bakhtiyor, Djumanova E. Nargiza.**
CHANGES IN THE MORPHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF THE GASTRIC MUCOSA AND THE BASE OF THE GASTRIC MUCOSA OF WHITE RATS IN POLYPRAGMAZY.....355
49. **Ismailova A. Jadida, Ermekbaeva U. Arkbal, Zinatdinova K. Indira.**
STUDY OF MORPHOLOGICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF EOSINOPHILIC ESOPHAGITIS.....361

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

50. **Makhkamov N.J., Nazarov I.R.**
CLINICAL-MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE AVASCULAR NECROSIS OF THE SON SUEBEA AFFECTED BY COVID-19.....367
51. **Tilyakov A. Xasan, Tilyakov B. Aziz, Temurov A. Alisher, Shukurov N. Fayzullakhon.**
EXPERIENCE IN PERFORMING OPERATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH A FRACTURE OF THE PROXIMAL FEMUR WITH A RISK OF DEEP VEIN THROMBOSIS.....372

52. **Husainboev D. Shokhrukhbek.**
SYMPTOMS, ETIOLOGY AND TYPES OF TREATMENT OF SHOULDER JOINT INJURY INJURIES (LITERATURE REVIEW).....379

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

53. **Turonov S. Bobur, Iskandarova A. Malika.**
IRIDOLOGY AS A PROMISING DIAGNOSTIC METHOD IN CLINICAL PRACTICE AND FORENSIC MEDICINE (LITERATURE REVIEW).....385
54. **Turonov S. Bobur, Iskandarov I. Alisher.**
VISCERO-IRIDAL REFLEX CONNECTIONS IN THE MECHANISM OF IRIDOLOGY VISCERO-IRIDAL REFLEX CONNECTIONS IN THE MECHANISM OF IRIDOLOGY.....391
55. **Indiaminov I. Sayit, Kamalov Sh. Sherzod.**
CURRENT STATE OF FORENSIC MEDICAL DIAGNOSTICS OF INJURIES RESULTING FROM FALLS FROM A MOVING VEHICLE (LITERATURE REVIEW).....396

ENDOCRINOLOGY

56. **Kholikova O. Adliya, Halimova Yu. Zamira, Mavlyanova U. Gulkhida, Negmatova Sh. Gulzoda.**
COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF DIAGNOSTIC RESULTS IN PATIENTS WITH ACROMEGALY ACCORDING TO THE REGISTRY DATA.....403

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

57. **Dzhumaeva S. Nasiba, Karamatullaeva E. Zebo.**
CONSEQUENCES OF MUMPS INFECTION IN ADULTS (BASED ON THE EXAMPLE OF SAMARKAND REGION).....412
58. **Samibaeva Kh. Umida.**
THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION IN THE NEW CORONAVIRUS INFECTION COVID-19 (LITERATURE REVIEW).....420
59. **Yarmuxamedova K. Mahbuba, Yakubova S. Nigina, Kuchkarova A. Shirina, Baymirzaev I. Abdusodik.**
CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MEASLES IN THE SAMARKAND REGION.....428

OPHTHALMOLOGY

60. **Allayarov T. Azimbek, Rizaev A. Jasur, Yusupov A. Amin.**
ASSESSMENT OF STATISTICAL DATA ON DIABETIC RETINOPATHY IN SAMARKAND.....434

UROLOGY

61. **Gafarov R. Rushen.**
PHARMACOLOGICAL AND CLINICAL ASPECTS OF PHOSPHODIESTERASE TYPE 5 INHIBITORS IN THE TREATMENT OF ERECTILE DYSFUNCTION.....439

CLINICAL PHARMACOLOGY

62. **Saidova A. Shakhnoza, Musayeva J. Lola, Pulatova I. Nargiza, Pulatova B. Durдона, Abdusamatova Z. Dilorom, Avazova N. Gulchekhra.**
CLINICAL PHARMACOLOGY OF MINERALOCORTICOID RECEPTOR ANTAGONISTS AND THEIR USE IN TREATMENT OF INTERNAL DISEASE PATHOLOGY.....451

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ANTISEPTICS IN THE TREATMENT OF PURULENT COMPLICATIONS AFTER ABDOMINAL OPERATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The main criterion by which the effectiveness of the therapy was evaluated was the duration of the patient's treatment in the hospital. In the main group, it was significantly less - 12 days (in the control group - 21). Undoubtedly, in most cases, patients are not in the hospital until the skin edges of the wound are completely healed. A small skin defect in the absence of a deep wound tract and purulent discharge can be sanitized on an outpatient basis. In patients of the main group, already after the first dressings with Decasan, the symptoms of intoxication (general weakness, fatigue, headache) disappeared, the volume of discharge from the wound and the manifestations of the infectious inflammatory process (hyperemia, perifocal edema, tissue infiltration) significantly decreased.

Keywords. resistant strains of microorganisms, dekasane, abdominal surgery, local antiseptic for the treatment, purulent complications.

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АНТИСЕПТИКИ В ПРОФИЛАКТИКЕ ГНОЙНЫХ ОСЛОЖНЕНИЙ ПОСЛЕ БРЮШНЫХ ОПЕРАЦИЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Основным критерием, по которому оценивалась эффективность терапии, была длительность лечения пациента в стационаре. В основной группе он был существенно меньше – 12 дней (в контрольной – 21). Несомненно, в большинстве случаев больные не попадают в больницу до

полного заживления кожных краев раны. Небольшой дефект кожи при отсутствии глубоких раневых ходов и гнойных выделений можно санировать в амбулаторных условиях. У больных основной группы уже после первых перевязок Декасаном исчезли симптомы интоксикации (общая слабость, утомляемость, головная боль), объем выделений из раны и проявления инфекционно-воспалительного процесса (гиперемия, перифокальный отек, тканевая инфильтрация) значительно уменьшилась.

Ключевые слова. Резистентные штаммы микроорганизмов, декасан, абдоминальная хирургия, местный антисептик для лечения, гнойные осложнения.

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QORIN BO'SHLIG'IDAGI OPERATSIYALARDAN SO'NG YIRINGLI ASORATLARNI DAVOLASHDA QO'LLANILADIGAN ANTISEPTIKLAR

ANNOTATSIYA

Terapiya samaradorligini baholashning asosiy mezoni bemorning shifoxonada davolanish muddatidir. Asosiy guruhda u sezilarli darajada kamroq - 12 kun (nazorat guruhida - 21). Shubhasiz, aksariyat hollarda bemorlar yaraning teri qirralari to'liq davolanmaguncha kasalxonada emas. Chuqur yara yo'li va yiringli oqindi yo'qligida kichik teri nuqsoni ambulatoriya sharoitida sanitarizatsiya qilinishi mumkin. Asosiy guruhdagi bemorlarda, Dekasan bilan birinchi bog'lanishdan so'ng, intoksikatsiya belgilari (umumiy zaiflik, charchoq, bosh og'rig'i) yo'qoladi, yaradan oqindi miqdori va yuqumli yallig'lanish jarayonining namoyon bo'lishi (giperemiya, perifokal shish, to'qimalarning infiltratsiyasi) sezilarli darajada kamayadi.

Kalit so'zlar. mikroorganizmlarning chidamli shtammlari, dekasani, qorin bo'shlig'i jarrohligi, davolash uchun mahalliy antiseptik, yiringli asoratlar.

Jarrohlikdagi operatsiyadan keyingi yiringli muammolarni oldini olish va davolash masalasi bugungi kungacha dolzarb bo'lib qolmoqda. Buning asosiy sababi ilg'or texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda murakkab muolajalar sonining ko'payishi, shuningdek, jarrohlik aralashuvlar hajmi va davomiyligining oshishi hisoblanadi. Bu omillar to'qimalarning shikastlanishi va qon yo'qotishining kuchayishi bilan birga keladi, bu esa o'z navbatida operatsiyadan keyingi yara infeksiyalarining paydo bo'lishiga olib keladi. Qorin bo'shlig'i bo'shlig'i bo'shlig'i jarrohligida operatsiyadan keyingi yiringli asoratlarning chastotasi odatda 6% dan 8% gacha ("toza" muolajalarda 0,8% dan 2% gacha, ifloslanganlarda esa 20% gacha) [2, 4, 7].

Aniqlangan patogenlarga oltin stafilokokklar, koagulaz-manfiy stafilokokklar, *Enterococcus* spp. va *Escherichia coli* kiradi. Antimikrobiyal bintlardan foydalanish metitsillinga chidamli *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) va *Candida albicans* [8] sabab bo'lgan operatsiyadan keyingi yara muammolarini hal qilishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Aseptik va antiseptik protokollarga qat'iy rioya qilinishiga qaramay, jarrohlik yaralari mikroorganizmlar tomonidan ifloslanishga moyil. 80-90% hollarda yaralar har xil turdagi mikroorganizmlar bilan yuqadi, eng ko'p uchraydigan stafilokokklar [9].

Yarada infeksiyaning rivojlanishi nafaqat patogen turiga, balki organizmning umumiy holatiga va shikastlangan to'qimalarning funktsional holatiga ham bog'liq. Keng spektrli antibiotiklardan keng foydalanish kasallik joyidan yoki bemorning mikroflorasidan chidamli populyatsiyaning paydo bo'lishiga yordam berish qobiliyati bilan keng tan olingan. Sanitariya-gigiyena qoidalariga rioya qilinmasa, mikroblarning chidamli shtammlari jarrohlik zonasidagi narsalar orqali bir bemordan ikkinchi bemorga yuqishi mumkin. Bemor jarrohlik shifoxonasida bo'lganidan keyin 48 soat ichida ko'pchilik antibiotiklarga chidamli mikroblar shifoxonaning kirish

eshiklarida (teri, nafas olish yo'llari va ovqat hazm qilish kanali) topiladi.

Bunday hollarda mahalliy terapiya uchun antiseptik preparatlardan foydalanish juda muhimdir. Antibiotiklarning ahamiyatini qayta ko'rib chiqish davrida infeksiyalarning oldini olish va ularni davolash uchun antiseptik vositalardan foydalanishga qiziqish yangilandi. Dekametoksin (Dekametoksinum) terapevtik amaliyotda muhim antiseptik hisoblanadi. Bu juda kuchli va tez ta'sir qiluvchi bis-to'rtlamchi ammoniy hosilasidir. Preparat sintetik dekametilen molekulasi yarmidan va yalpiz moyining mentol efiridan iborat. Dekametoksin ko'pincha 0,02% eritma shaklida mavjud bo'lib, u Ukraina biznesi YURIA-PHARM tomonidan Dekasan sifatida sotiladi. Dekasan akromatik, diafan eritma bo'lib, har bir mililitrda 0,2 milligramm dekametoksin mavjud. Dekasan - qo'ziqorin, protozoa, virus va mikroorganizmlarga qarshi samarali dori. Dekasan maqsadli hujayra membranasining fosfatid guruhlaridagi lipid tuzilmalariga birlashtirish orqali ishlaydi, bu esa o'z navbatida membrananing o'tkazuvchanligini buzadi. Hujayra lizisi hujayra membranasining o'tkazuvchanligining buzilishi tufayli sodir bo'ladi, bu esa o'z navbatida hujayralar ichidagi gomeostazni buzadi. Dekasanning gramm-musbat va gramm-manfiy patogenlarning keng doirasiga nisbatan bakteritsid ta'siri chuqur o'rganilgan va tasdiqlangan. Mikroorganizmlarning ba'zilar stafilokokklar, streptokokklar, difteriya, Pseudomonas aeruginosa va boshqalarni o'z ichiga oladi. Dekasan epidermofitlar, trixofitlar, xamirturushga o'xshash zamburug'lar, eritrazma, xamirturush va ba'zi mog'orlarga qarshi fungitsid ta'sirini ko'rsatadi. Dekasan Giardia va Trichomonasga qarshi antiprotozoal faollikni namoyish etadi. Dekasan davolash jarayonida bakteriyalarning antibiotiklarga sezuvchanligini oshiradi va terapiyaga qarshilik ko'rsatgan shtammlarga qarshi samaradorlikni namoyish etadi.

Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi "Yosh olim" tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan Dekasan mahsulotining samaradorligi va xavfsizligini baholashdir. 14 raqami 148 ga teng. 2017 yil aprel oyida qorin bo'shlig'idagi operatsiyalardan keyin yuzaga keladigan yiringli muammolarni davolash uchun Ukrainadan "YURIA-FARM" deb nomlangan dori tasdiqlangan. Eksperimental jarayonlar va texnikalar. Tadqiqot 19 yoshdan 68 yoshgacha bo'lgan jami 39 bemorni qamrab oldi, ulardan 22 nafari ayollar va 17 nafari erkaklar. Kalkulyoz xoletsistit bo'yicha 9 nafar (23%) bemorga, appendektomiya bo'yicha 18 nafar (46,1%), o'tkir ichak tutilishi bilan 8 nafar (20%), churrani tuzatish bo'yicha 4 nafar (10,3%) bemorga jarrohlik muolajalari o'tkazildi. Bemorlar ikki guruhga bo'lingan: 22 kishidan iborat asosiy guruh va 17 kishidan iborat nazorat guruhi. Birlamchi kogortada Dekasan mahalliy lashtirilgan terapiya uchun qo'llanilgan, nazorat guruhida yarani tozalash xlorheksidin biglyukonatning 0,05% eritmasi yordamida o'tkazildi. Drenaj naychalari orqali yara bo'shliqlarini tozalash, turundalar yordamida yara kanallarini dezinfeksiya qilish, shuningdek yaralarni bo'shashmasdan o'rash uchun antiseptiklar qo'llanilgan. Agar zarur bo'lsa, har kuni ko'p marta kiyinish qo'llaniladi.

Ikkala guruhga ham qo'llaniladigan terapiya bir xil bo'lib, antibakterial, detoksifikatsiya qiluvchi, yallig'lanishga qarshi, immunomodulyatsion va desensibilizatsiya qiluvchi moddalarni qo'llashdan iborat edi. Yaralarni davolash tozalikni ta'minlash, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri zararlangan hududga antiseptiklarni qo'llash va infeksiyalangan yoki o'lik to'qimalarni to'g'ri drenajlash va olib tashlashni o'z ichiga oladi. Bundan tashqari, bemorlar qandli diabet, gipertenziya, koronar arteriya kasalligi va anemiya kabi kasalliklar uchun terapiya oldilar. Yarani davolash dinamikasini baholash klinik, sitologik, bakteriologik va bakterioskopik tadqiqot usullaridan foydalangan holda o'tkazildi. Bemorlarni kasalxonaga yotqizish muddati, asoratlarning paydo bo'lishi va xususiyatlari, jarohatlarning bitish tezligi, antiseptiklarni mahalliy qo'llashga bemorlarning sub'ektiv munosabati kabi omillar ko'rib chiqildi. Har ikki guruhdagi yara oqmalarining bakteriologik tahlili 19 (50%) holatda E. coli, 6 (15,8%) holatda stafilokokk, 7 (18,4%) holatda Proteus, 4 (7,9%) holatda Pseudomonas aeruginosa borligini ko'rsatdi.) hollarda, 2 (5,2%) holatda bakteroid, 1 (2,6%) holatda anaerob klostridiya. 29 bemorda monokultura aniqlangan, bu holatlarning 76,3% ni tashkil qiladi, 9 bemorda esa mikrobia aloqalar aniqlangan, bu 23,7% hollarda.

Natijalar va uning muhokamasi. Terapiyaning samaradorligini baholash uchun ishlatiladigan asosiy o'lchov bemorning kasalxonaga yotqizish muddati edi. Asosiy guruhda farq sezilarli bo'lib, 21 kunga kamaygan nazorat guruhiga nisbatan 12 kunga kamaygan. Odatda, bemorlar

kesmaning teri chegaralari to'liq tuzalmaguncha kasalxonadan chiqarilmaydi. Chuqur yara kanali va yiringsiz terining kichik nuqsoni ambulatoriya sharoitida dezinfektsiya qilinishi mumkin. Decasan sarg'ishlarini dastlabki qo'llashdan so'ng, asosiy guruhdagi bemorlarda intoksikatsiya bilan bog'liq simptomlar (umumiy zaiflik, charchoq va bosh og'rig'i kabi) tezda bartaraf etilgan. Bundan tashqari, yaraning oqishi hajmi sezilarli darajada kamaygan va yuqumli yallig'lanish belgilari, shu jumladan qizarish, yara atrofida shishish va to'qimalarning infiltratsiyasi kamaygan.

Mikroskopik tasvir qulay bakteriologik va sitologik o'zgarishlarni ko'rsatdi. Davolashning ikkinchi-uchinchi kunida preparatlar fagotsitar faollikni namoyon etdi, bu alohida fagotsitar hujayralar va gistiyositik komponentlarning mavjudligidan dalolat beradi. Neytrofil granulotsitlar va bakteriyalar sonining kamayishi kuzatildi. Ushbu vaqt oralig'ida nazorat guruhida sitologik ko'rinishda foydali o'zgarishlar kuzatilmadi. Klinik, bakteriologik va sitologik testlar natijalari Decasan dan foydalanishning xlorheksidin biglyukonatdan ustunligini aniq ko'rsatib turibdi. Terapiya davomida Dekasandan foydalanish bilan bog'liq hech qanday salbiy ta'sir yoki allergik reaksiyalar aniqlanmadi. Dekametoksinning 0,02% konsentratsiyasida zararli ta'sirining yo'qligi va moddaning ozgina singishi bunga sababdir.

Xulosa.

1. Decasan qorin bo'shlig'i operatsiyasidan keyingi bemorlarda mahalliy sifatida qo'llanilganda foydali terapevtik ta'sirga ega ekanligi aniqlandi. Bu jarohatni davolashning tezlashishi va kasalxonaga yotqizish muddatining qisqarishida namoyon bo'ldi.

2. Dekasan antibakterial, antifungal va virusga qarshi xususiyatlarning keng spektri, shuningdek minimal yon ta'siri va allergik reaksiyalar tufayli operatsiyadan keyingi yiringli yaralarni davolash uchun mahalliy antiseptik sifatida tavsiya etiladi.

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